

Drishti: the Sight

Vol.- X, Issue - I, (May, 2021-October, 2021)

(UGC-CARE listed Journal)

**A REFEREED (PEER-REVIEWED) BI-ANNUAL NATIONAL RESEARCH
JOURNAL OF ENGLISH LITERATURE/ASSAMESE LITERATURE/FOLKLORE /CULTURE**

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(A NON-PROFIT VENTURE DEDICATED TO THE CAUSE OF EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH
PARTICULARLY AMONG THE YOUNG SCHOLARS OF THE NATION)

Published by :
Ms. Rupjyoti Goswami

Chief Editor (Hon.) :
Dr. Dipak Jyoti Baruah

Price : # Single: Rs. 700/-
#One Year Subscription: Rs. 1400/-

Printed at :
Printed at : Sri Ganesh Printers, Noonmati, Guwahati-781020 (Assam)

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ড° মহেশ্বৰ কলিতা

EDITORIAL

Online Transaction of Teaching-learning during Pandemic

In view of the second wave of the pandemic, it is certain that the online transaction of teaching-learning is here to stay. The learners are by this time to some extent conditioned to such a situation following their hour of bafflement caused by the first wave. Students are the main stakeholders of an educational institution and they must get respite from their anxiety over the possible academic fallouts arising out of the presence of the pandemic.

The authorities therefore must make objective planning to find ways about how best they could provide the teachers and the students with the necessary infrastructural facilities, viz. skill, trainings, internet connectivity, tools, and knowledge resources. There is spreading lockdown and the unpredictability of the situation weighs heavy upon the minds of the people in general. However, even at this juncture, in our country, most of the hinterlands reel under connectivity-crisis in terms of internet facilities. The government must therefore wake up to the situation and by taking cue of the situation explore the ways of providing equitable opportunities in online academic transactions through proper IT planning. The Universities too need to gear themselves up to create some standardized pools of knowledge-resources in view of the present circumstances. The objective should be not just to deliver functional contents to the learners but also to be confident of themselves about the resources given as being genuine, relevant, well-researched and well written. The university departments may also research and select from the available data available in the various platforms on the internet for providing them to the students in conformity with the syllabi in use (the university/College departments and libraries may come with lists of websites and links, which the students can depend upon without an iota of doubt. In this regard, policies may be adopted for mobilizing the services of the prominent universities and libraries of the world for international exchange of educational data at a greater level).

Academics need also adopt appropriate methodologies to facilitate their academic transaction. Universities and colleges may also arrange for training and orientation sessions for the faculties regarding online teaching.

Another notable concern is also that in view of suspension of physical mode of classroom learning, there is possibility of stress in the mind of the students. The institutions can also think of engaging one or two psychological counselors to reach out to those learners, who may be available in need of supports in case of stress and trauma arising out of the new familial and social environment during the pandemic. #

Focus area for November, 2021 issue

GENDER AND ITS REPRESENTATION IN LITERATURE AND POPULAR CULTURE

Gender has been an issue, inextricably related in various forms to literature and popular culture. Gender as a cultural concept cuts across the traditional notion of a 'man' or a 'woman'. It has rather encompassed all kinds of human existence. In the post modern era, gender is looked as a performance. Judith Butler opines that the subject is a product of discourse and a performative construct. Following the Derridian notion of deference, Butler postulates that the subject never achieves its completion. It is caught up in the process of constant deferral and differentiation. If the subject never achieves its completion, gender can only be an effect of discourse and not the cause of discourse. Thus gender is a crucial determinant in the production, circulation and consumption of literary and cultural discourses.

Popular culture is a contested site. On the one hand, it refers to the cultural practices of lived culture that people engage in. On the other hand, popular culture also refers to the cultural texts which are symbolic and whose function is the production of meaning through words, images or practices. Popular culture, as a fluid concept, encompasses a large number of cultural texts and practices ranging from films to newspaper articles, computer games to music, mass media like Television, Radio, the Press and the emerging social media et al.

Representation is a process of communication that depicts or describes something or someone. In the literary as well as cultural arena, language and images are the key symbolic systems through which representations are made. Representation is crucial in the creation of meanings. Thus, representations are constructed through language, images and socio-cultural practices, and possess a material as well as symbolic dimension. (Milestone & Meyer, 2012:8)

Incorporating these concepts and their diverse dimensions and notions of gender and representation in literature and popular culture, **Drishti: the Sight** intends to reflect upon the theme from multidimensional perspectives and newer theoretical paradigms. Scholars are invited to contribute their original scholarly research papers on any possible topic within the focus area for the next issue of the Journal to be published in November, 2021.

Scholars are requested to submit their papers by following the norms (please read the 'Mode of Submission' portion in the Call for Papers on this website). FOR PAPER SUBMISSION, THE WINDOW WILL REMAIN OPEN FOR THE PERIOD BETWEEN JUNE, 15 AND JULY, 05, 2021 ON THIS WEBSITE.

(Contributors may also submit papers on subjects other than this focus area for the forthcoming November issue. Regarding the modalities to be followed for submission, they are requested to go through the CFP published on this website).